

THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *This paper discusses two foreign language teaching technologies: cooperative learning and the project method.*

Key words: *project method, cooperative learning, foreign language, English.*

The Republic of Uzbekistan is building a democratic state governed by the rule of law and an open civil society, ensuring respect for human rights and freedoms, the spiritual renewal of society, the formation of a socially oriented market economy and integration into the world community. On 10 December 2012, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" was adopted, which mainly dealt with the status of the English language.

It was noted in the document that under the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the National Program of training a comprehensive system of foreign language teaching is being actively implemented in the country, aimed at forming a harmoniously developed, highly educated, modern-minded younger generation, further integrating the country into the global community.

Awareness of the need to know at least one foreign language has come to our society. For any specialist, if he/she wants to succeed in his/her field, knowledge of a foreign language is vital. Therefore, the motivation to learn it has increased dramatically. However, the difficulties in mastering a foreign language, especially in the mass school, have not diminished. Still the main ones are: the lack of active oral practice per student in the group, the lack of necessary individualization and differentiation of training. Teachers of the new generation must be able to skillfully select and apply those technologies that fully correspond to the content and objectives of the study of a particular discipline, contribute to the goals of harmonious development of students, taking into account their individual characteristics.

The concept "pedagogical technology" can be considered in three aspects: scientific - as a part of pedagogical science, which studies and develops goals, content and methods of training and designs pedagogical processes; procedural - as a description (algorithm) of the process, a set of goals, content, methods and means of achieving the planned learning outcomes; active - implementation of technological (pedagogical) process, functioning of all personal, instrumental and methodological teaching tools.

Like any technology, pedagogical technology is a process in which there is a qualitative change in the impact on the learner. Pedagogical technology can be represented by the following formula: $PT = \text{goals} + \text{objectives} + \text{content} + \text{methods (techniques, means)} + \text{forms of learning}$ Compared to teaching based on methodology, teaching technology has serious advantages. The basis of technology is a clear definition of the final goal. In traditional pedagogy, the problem of goals is not leading, the degree of achievement is defined imprecisely, "by eye". In technology the goal is considered as a central component, which allows you to define the degree of its achievement more accurately. Technology, in which the goal (final and intermediate) is defined very precisely (diagnosable), allows developing objective methods of controlling its achievement. The technology allows minimizing the situations when the teacher is put before the choice and is forced to move to pedagogical impromptu in search of an acceptable option.

In contrast to previously used methodological lesson plans that focus on the teacher and his/her activities, the technology offers a learning process project that defines the structure and content of students' learning and cognitive activities. Every teacher perceives methodical lesson plans differently; consequently, students' activities are organized differently. Designing students' learning activities, on the other hand, leads to higher stability of success of almost any number of students. "Personality-oriented approach implies flexibility in setting goals, takes into account students' personal interests and individual characteristics and creates prerequisites for greater learning outcomes. This approach creates a special relationship between students and teachers and between students themselves, and creates a variety of learning and educational environments, often extending beyond the classroom and school. Person-centred learning includes project-based learning, collaborative learning and multigrade learning.

Collaborative learning.

The ideology of collaborative learning has been developed in detail by three groups of American educators: R. Slavin from Johns Hopkins University; R. Johnson and D. Johnson from the University of Minnesota; the group of E. Aronson from California State University. "The main idea of this technology is to create conditions for active collaborative learning

activities of students in different learning situations. Pupils are different: some "grasp" all explanations of the teacher quickly, easily master the lexical material and communicative skills; others need not only much more time to comprehend the material, but also additional examples and explanations. Such children, as a rule, are shy to ask questions in front of the whole class, and sometimes they simply do not realize what exactly they do not understand, they cannot formulate a correct question. If in such cases children are divided into small groups (3-4 persons) and given a common task, stipulating the role of each pupil of the group in completing this task, then there is a situation in which everyone is responsible not only for the result of his work (which often leaves a pupil indifferent), but, most importantly, for the result of the group. That is why weak pupils try to find out from the strong pupils all the questions that they do not understand and the strong ones are interested in making sure that all the group members, in particular the weak pupil, thoroughly understand the material (at the same time giving the strong pupil a chance to check his own understanding and to get to the heart of the matter). In this way, joint efforts are made to fill in gaps. This is the general idea of cooperative learning.

The idea of collaborative learning has been developed by many educators in many countries around the world, because the idea itself is extremely humanistic in nature and therefore pedagogical, although variations from country to country are noticeable. So, here are some options for collaborative learning "Student team learning (STL). In this variant of cooperative learning implementation the emphasis is placed on "team goals" and team success, which can be achieved only as a result of independent work of each group member (team) in constant interaction with other students of the same group while working on the topic/problem/issue to be studied. Variants of this approach can be considered: a) individual-group (student - teams - achievement divisions - STAD) and b) team-game (teams - games - tournament - TGT) work".

Another variant of organizing cooperative learning was developed by Professor E. Aronson in 1978 and called it Jigsaw. In pedagogical practice this approach is abbreviated as Jigsaw. Students are organized into groups of 4-6 to work on the learning material, which is divided into fragments (logical or semantic blocks). Such work in lessons is organized at the stage of creative application of language material. Each member of the group finds material on their sub-topic. Then students studying the same issue but working in different groups meet and exchange information as experts on the issue. This is called an "expert meeting". Then they go back to their groups and tell their peers in the group what they have learned. They, in their turn, talk about their part of the task. All communication is in a foreign language.

Each student individually and the team as a whole reports on the whole topic. "Another variant of collaborative learning - learning together - was developed at the University of Minnesota in 1987 (D. Johnson and R. Johnson). The class is divided into groups of 3-4 people. Each group is given one assignment that is part of some larger topic that the whole class is working on. Each group is given the task of preparing its part. As a result of the joint work of the individual groups and the whole group, a full assimilation of the material is achieved. One should keep in mind that all the necessary vocabulary on the topic has been learned during previous work in other lessons. The basic ideas inherent in all the co-operative learning options described here enable the teacher to be learner-centred. This is the learner-centred approach in the classroom, one of the possible ways of implementing it. When collaborative learning is used, the most difficult thing is to get pupils in small groups to communicate in the foreign language. But practice shows that with enough persistent attention from the teacher this requirement is fulfilled at first with difficulty and then gradually with evident pleasure. It should be noted that it is not enough to form groups and give them an appropriate task. The essence is that the student himself/herself wants to acquire knowledge. **The project method** belongs to the methods and consequently to the technologies of personality-centered approach in teaching foreign languages. The project method is a set of educational and cognitive methods that allow solving a particular problem as a result of students' independent actions with the obligatory presentation of these results. Project technology includes a set of research, search, problem methods, creative by their very essence". It is known that learning a foreign language contributes significantly to overall development. The project method is the essence of developmental, personality-centered learning. The quiz conducted at foreign language lessons, in our opinion, represents a synthesis of creative, research and information project method. The quiz as a research project method gives the students an opportunity to participate in the research quest. Quiz gives the teacher an opportunity of informal contact with the students, who are more easy and accessible to it when they are busy with something interesting, helps to build trusting relationships, to build communication on the basis of friendly disposition.

The use of innovative forms of learning in contrast to traditional methods gives the student the main role on the way to knowledge assimilation, in which the teacher is an active assistant, organizes, directs and stimulates the learning activity. In his activity the teacher has to solve not only educational tasks, but also to create conditions for an independent and creative search of knowledge, to stimulate students to research activity, to form skills of orientation in a huge informational space and

independent decision-making. The introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process is considered as a necessary condition for solving these tasks. A constantly developing system of information support combined with technical support ensures the quality of the educational process.

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